

Author: Michelle Ramirez Lopez

Gender variations

There are different theories about the difference between the way of speaking in the gender. It is necessary to know to try to understand the differences that exists between both languages. Much research of this matter wonder if gender has to do with the process of learning a language for instance English. Do these differences and similarities play an important role of a language.

There are different conditions were performing masculinity or femininity appropriately can differ from what the expectations are. In fact, it is closely related to the circumstances such as company, public or private spaces, social and economic positions or simply the relation that is held for the group of people gathered and many other features related to this.

Females have two X chromosomes whereas males have an X and a Y; this is a key genetic difference, and no geneticist regards that difference as unimportant. On average, females have more fat and less muscle than males, are not as strong, and weigh less. They also mature more rapidly and live longer. The female voice usually has different characteristics from the male voice, and often females and males exhibit different ranges of verbal skills. Wardhaugh, R. (2006)

This document reveals that Women and men develop different patterns of language use. Moreover, females tend to focus on the affective functions of an interaction more often than men do. Softer linguistic devices being used by women that stress solidarity more often than men express soft manners. And finally, girls tend to interact in ways which will maintain and increase solidarity, while, especially in formal contexts, boys tend to interact in ways which will maintain and increase their power and status.

As a matter of fact, there are scientific proofs that women and men are biologically different and so their language. But it is true that this is a process because since boy and girls are very young they are taught to use some words to behave in a certain way the promotes

the use of some specific language for that reason when the person is growing up adopts certain characteristic proper of the gender that have a big influence over the use of words. Education is seemed the same way, but it tries to standardize the content for everyone to get a state of general understanding no matter if for one language is useful or nice to hear or to do. At the end it provokes another way of communication to have diversity of language regardless its gender.

References:

Wardhaugh, R. (2006). *An Introduction to Sociolinguistics*. Fifth edition. Blackwell Publishing.